

Common Habits Of Mind Of The First Year Of Secondary Students In The Gifted Centers In Qassim Region

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: November 26, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: January 18, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords Habits of Mind , Gifted Students.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4448404</p>	<p><i>The present study aimed to find out the common habits of mind and deployed to the first grade of secondary students in the Gifted centers in the Qassim region according to sex , and to achieve the goal of the study was the use of Habits of Mind scale , consisting of sixteen usually mentality and all usually followed by four statements according to the classification (Costa &Kallick, 2000) , And reached the study sample (238) Distributors (123) students, (115) students from first grade secondary students , and the results showed the prevalence of habits of mind among the first grade of secondary students in the Gifted centers in the Qassim region highly , and according to the results of the study were usually (permanent readiness for continuous learning) is the highest prevalent , while she was usually "think beyond the cognitive " less prevalent , and the results showed not no statistically significant differences in the common habits of mind differences between first-grade secondary students in the Gifted centers in the Qassim region due to gender (Male , Female) , The study came up with several recommendations.</i></p>

1. Introduction

The challenges of the age imposed on educators and decision-makers to deal with the process of (learning - education) as a need that continues with the individual, and as a necessity to facilitate his adaptation to the developments he faces in his surroundings in which he lives. The slogans of "Teaching the Student How to Learn" and "Teaching the Student How to think" came with important implications that predict a better future for individuals and groups. This led the educational institutions represented by schools and universities to work on including the plans and teaching programs offered by courses to teach thinking and creativity. (Jerwan, 2013)

Scholars and educational researchers have differed views on the definition of thinking. They presented different definitions based on multiple theoretical directions, as De Bono (2003).

The habits of mind are the system that arranges business affairs, its priorities and puts them in the context in which they should be. The habits of mind shows the need for there to be a mental system to think about the course of events, and the extent to which the learner needs training on this system, until it becomes a habit that is implemented in a semi-routine mechanical way, just as the mental system is part of the habits of Mind that he practices daily. Good habits of mind are essential for everyone throughout their personal, social and family life path. (Costa &Kallick, 2000)

The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia has paid attention to the development of talented people, as they can contribute to the advancement of their homeland and their nation by providing them with stimulating environments for creativity, innovation and discovery, and other aspects of talent. Special centers have been prepared for them to reveal, care for and guide them (Lala, Ziyad, and Saeb, 2013).

The concept of habits of mind:

Costa &Kallick (2008) define habits of mind as the tendency of an individual to act in an intelligent manner when confronted with a problem, when the answer or solution is not available in cognitive structures. The problem may be in the form of a confusing situation, a mystery.

The concept of talent: -

From the educational point of view, the first internationally recognized educational definition of gifted came to state: that gifted children are that category that enjoys outstanding performance and achievement compared to the age group to which it belongs and / or one or more of the following abilities: general mental abilities, specialized academic performance, abilities Creative, artistic, leadership, physical / psychological ability. (Al-Suroor, 2009).

- Previous studies:

Trad (2012) conducted a study aimed at uncovering the impact of the (Costa and Calic) program on developing creative thinking using habits of mind among third-stage students in the College of Physical Education. The results showed that the Costa and Calic program has a positive effect on teaching and developing creative thinking using habits of male and female students in the third stage of the Faculty of

Physical Education. The results also showed that the educational program has the same effect on developing creative thinking by using habits of male and female students.

- Muheisen(2010)conducted a study aimed at investigating the level of students' acquisition of habits of mind in the upper elementary stage according to the Global Project 2061, on grades (fifth, seventh, and ninth) and its relationship to the grade variable, gender and school achievement, and the results showed statistically significant differences attributed to a variable Achievement in the acquisition of habits of mind in favor of high-achieving students, and gender variable in favor of females.

-Weirsema (2009) conducted a study entitled Intentional Mental Processing: Students' thinking about one of the habits of the mind. The study sample consisted of eight university students participating in a university course, and the study used observation and interview in the data collection process, and the results of the study indicated that the teaching of students The best way to ask a question is the best way to develop the habits of mind for them, and for students to learn to ask and answer difficult questions on their own, and then develop mental processing processes lead to the development of the student's habits of mind.

The study Problem:

The results of the research on habits of mind clearly indicate the focus of the use and application of the study of habits of Mind in different fields of science and at different levels of study. That is why the sixteen habits were used in this study, because they are not practiced in isolation from each other, as Costa pointed out, and they are necessary and appropriate for all. The academic stages, which need to be used on the group of gifted students, especially in light of the rapid and increasing change in the growth of knowledge, and the need for complex and varied skills in the labor market in the twenty-first century, all of this has made a great interest in developing strategies that keep pace with the changing needs of students in general and gifted students in a way. In particular, it contributes to enhancing and improving their ability to solve problems and adapt to the requirements of the labor market.

That is why the problem of the study lies in knowing the extent of the prevalence of the habits of the mind among first grade students of high school gifted in gifted care centers in the Qassim region, by answering the following study questions:

Study questions:

The first question: What are the common habits of mind among first-grade students in the gifted care centers in Al-Qassim region?

- The second question: Are there statistically significant differences in the habits of mind common among first-grade secondary students in gifted care centers in the Qassim region due to gender?

Objectives of the study:

1- To uncover the habits of mind that are common and widespread among first-grade students in the gifted care centers in the Qassim region, and to know their arrangement according to their prevalence.

2- Finding out the differences in the habits of the mind that are common and widespread among first-grade secondary students in gifted care centers in the Qassim region, due to gender (male, female).

The importance of the study: The importance of the current study lies in the following:

1. The contemporary society of the information age and globalization needs great mental skills, and the challenges and implications of this technology require an education to think. The ordinary and talented students are immunized from the repercussions of this era in an integrated way, starting from childhood to postgraduate level, hence the idea of studying the habits of Mind benefits from what many theorists have called for its importance.

2. This study - within the limits of the researcher's knowledge - is the first study conducted on the habits of the mind among first-grade students of gifted secondary school in Gifted Care Centers in the Qassim region, and thus this research contributes to enriching the Saudi Library and trying to fill the deficiency in this area.

3. This study will provide teachers at the secondary level in general education with information about the common habits of mind and spread among students, and this will help them in processing this information through the content of the courses.

Method and procedures:

Study methodology: A survey approach was used to investigate the prevalence and prevalence of habits of mind on a sample of first grade secondary students in gifted care centers in the Qassim region.

Study community and sample:

The study population consists of all male and female students, from the first year of secondary school students enrolled in the gifted care centers in the Qassim region for the second semester of the year (2014-2015), and their number (750) students, and the study sample consisted of students of the first grade of secondary school Enrolled in gifted care centers in the Qassim region, their number is (238) male and female students, which represent (32%) of the study population, distributed as follows, (123) students and (115) female students, and they were chosen by the intentional sample due to the presence of an understanding and cooperative

administration To conduct the study, Table No. (1) shows the distribution of the sample members according to the study variables.

Study variables:

The dependent variable:

the common habits of mind among first-grade students in the gifted care centers in the Qassim region, which is represented in the degree of students' performance (the study sample) on the scale of the habits of the mind.

- Statistical treatments: The study data were processed according to the following statistical methods: frequencies and percentages, arithmetic means and standard deviation, and (T) test.

Results related to the first question:

What are the common habits of mind among first-grade secondary students in gifted care centers in Al-Qassim region?

The results of analyzing the responses of first-grade secondary students in the gifted care centers in the Qassim region on the habits of mind questionnaire showed a rise in arithmetic averages on the habits of the mind. Arithmetic averages and standard deviations were extracted for the responses of students in the first grade of secondary school in the gifted care centers in the Qassim region, and these averages have been arranged in terms of their height in descending order to indicate the extent of their prevalence among high school students (gifted) as following :

among the students of the grade The first secondary school for both males and females in gifted care centers in the Qassim region, to a high degree. The results of the study are consistent with the results of the study of Al-Shammari (2010), the study of Muheisen (2010), and Al-Barsan (2012), which indicated the predominance of all habits of Mind among the study sample, and it was usually Metacognitive thinking is the least common habit among the study sample. The results of the current study coincide with the study of Al-Ayasrah (2012), which indicated the prevalence of habits of mind among the study sample. The most prevalent habits were usually persistence, thinking flexibly, questioning, posing problems and collecting data using the senses. While the habit of metacognitive thinking was the least common among female students, and these results are similar to the current study.

This result of the first question is consistent with the theoretical literature, which indicates that the prevalence of these habits among the study sample may be due to the fact that the curricula and training programs in the Gifted Care Centers in the Qassim region require students to enjoy these habits in order to achieve success and continue in these centers and join them. The prevalence of habits of mind on the study sample is high can be explained by the fact that gifted students enjoy a large degree of these habits, especially the habit (permanent and continuous learning), which obtained the highest habit spread among the study sample, which is one of the characteristics and characteristics of the students. Talented people. The habits of Mind can be attributed to a high degree that the Gifted Care Centers show a clear and great interest in the teaching and learning process, through training courses provided to teachers and supervisors in Gifted Care Centers, which focus on providing a safe learning environment for gifted students. In addition, family upbringing may play an important role in this direction, as for the habit of (metacognitive thinking), which came in the last place. The reason may be attributed to the fact that it reflects a perception that is predominantly philosophical, and this type of thinking is not available in abundance compared to the habit of (permanent and continuous learning) in the curricula and training programs provided to students in gifted care centers. Planning, monitoring and evaluation require greater skills than others, as teachers of the Gifted Care Centers have not been adequately trained to train students on them.

- Results related to the second question: Are there statistically significant differences in the habits of mind common among first grade secondary students in gifted care centers in the Qassim region due to gender (male, female)?

To answer this question, (T) test was performed on two independent samples in order to identify the differences in the habits of mind common among first-grade students in the gifted care centers in the Qassim region according to the difference between the sex variable as the following :

It is evident that the differences are in the habits of mind (perseverance, thinking and communicating clearly, controlling impulsivity, questioning and posing problems, responding with amazement and awe, thinking flexibly, collecting data using all the senses, striving for accuracy, thinking metacognitive, applying knowledge. The precedent in new situations, listening with understanding and sympathy, finding humor, creativity, perception and innovation, reciprocal thinking, constant readiness for continuous learning, taking responsible risks (whose values were in order) -0.63, -0.40, -1.71, 0.18, -0.99 0.06, -0.87, -0.60, 0.76, 0.30, -0.42, -0.16, 1.27, -1.63, 0.32, 1.46, -0.24) and all of these values are not significant at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) level or less. Therefore, there are no statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the habits of

mind common among first-grade students in the gifted care centers in the Qassim region due to gender (male, female).

The results of this question are consistent with the study of Al-Bursan (2010) in that all the habits of the mind except for the habit of (supra-cognitive thinking) in which there are no differences attributed to the gender variable between males and females, and the result of this question differs with the study of Al-Bursan (2010) where it was only one habit, which is a habit (metacognitive thinking) in favor of males in The tenth grade, the study of al-Shammari (2010) where there were differences of habits of mind in favor of males, and the study of Muheisen (2010) and the study of Karaki (2007) where there were differences of habits of mind in favor of females. Talented people are exposed to the same training programs, and because they belong to one administrative and supervisory area as well. Perhaps the explanation is also due to the presence of periodic meetings and follow-up by the Department of Giftedness Care of supervisors, teachers and teachers in Gifted Care Centers, and because of the existence of a prior plan by the Talented Department in the Qassim region, which they transfer Training on it for male and female students with the same goals, and the skills to be applied to students.

Recommendations:

In light of the results of the study, the researcher recommends the following:

- 1- The necessity of taking care of all the habits of mind, integrating them into the education process and presenting them within the training programs provided to gifted students.
- 2- Training male and female teachers on methods of developing the habits of mind among gifted students.
- 3- Conducting more research on the habits of the mind and methods of developing it among students of gifted care centers.
- 4- The necessity of integrating the habits of mind into school curricula as it is an educational goal that modern education seeks to achieve.

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